

Use of the Health Belief Model to examine willingness to use omega-3-enriched eggs

Marina Tomić Maksan, Branka Šakić Bobić, Damir Kovačić, Željka Mesić

University of Zagreb Faculty of Agriculture, Svetošimunska cesta 25, Zagreb, Croatia (matomic@agr.hr)

Summary

The market for functional foods is relatively young and growing, mainly due to increased consumer awareness of the importance of nutrition for human health. Omega-3 fatty acids are essential fatty acids that help to reduce the risk of heart disease and maintain normal blood cholesterol levels. The production of omega-3 fatty acid-enriched eggs requires a modification of the poultry feed, which usually involves the addition of fish and/or flaxseed oil and flaxseed. The aim of this study was to use the Health Belief Model (HBM) to determine the factors influencing the willingness to consume omega-3 enriched eggs. The data was collected from 159 respondents (egg purchasers) using a validated questionnaire. Multiple linear regression in the SPSS statistical package was used to analyse the relationships between the HBM constructs. The results showed that perceived benefits, severity, cue to action and self-efficacy had a significant impact on the willingness to use omega-3 enriched eggs. However, perceived barriers, health motivation and perceived susceptibility had no effect on willingness to use omega-3 enriched eggs. Promoting omega-3 enriched eggs by doctors and as tasty, easy available and beneficial for heart health is likely to trigger the willingness to use omega-3 enriched eggs.

Keywords: omega-3 enriched eggs, consumers, survey, health belief model

Acknowledgments: This research has been supported by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 952303 (AgriFoodBoost).